

THE ROLE OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ON QUALITY OF DECISIONS IN GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the reality of knowledge management and identifying the level of effectiveness of activities, and Highlight the role of knowledge management in the quality of decisions. This study relied on the descriptive analytical method. The questionnaire was developed for the purposes of collecting primary data, the study population consists of all government institutions in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and the number of these institutions is 135 government institutions, divided into 13 sectors. A random sample of (200) employees were distributed, from which (182) questionnaires were recovered and considered valid for testing. The findings of this study were: 1-The results showed that the government institutions in Jordan use knowledge management processes (knowledge diagnosis, knowledge planning, knowledge sharing, knowledge acquisition, storage and retrieval of knowledge, organization and follow-up of knowledge). 2-The results of the study showed that the government institutions succeeded during the last five years in achieving their goals through their various activities, taking into account that there is a disparity between the different sectors in the extent to which they achieve those goals. 3- The results showed a significant relationship between the applications of knowledge management and the quality of administrative decisions in government institutions in Jordan, as institutions that practice knowledge management and use it in their organizational life are more effective and able to achieve their goals than other institutions that do not practice knowledge management. In conclusion, this study concluded with a set of recommendations, which were drawn in light of the results, the most important of which was, the Government institutions should exchange knowledge among themselves through meetings, conferences and exchange of experiences.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Quality of Decisions, Government Institutions.

INTRODUCTION

The impact of knowledge management and quality of decisions in government institutions is related to change for the better, and aims to know the impact of these decisions on worker's skills, attitudes and behaviors, in order to advance the human element and help him to provide the best of his tender to contribute in achieving the goals sought by institutions.

Institutions operate in environments characterized by continuous change, and in order for these institutions to ensure their continued survival, we must study these variables and determine the extent of their positive and negative effects, whether on their performance, or on the emotional and material aspects of workers in institutions.

The various institutions seek to develop and renew knowledge through multiple training plans and programs, these plans and programs have received a lot of attention and study, whether with regard to their method, or the method of their implementation, this was related to the role of quality and decisions, their impact and the degree of their effectiveness to acquire specific skills, and then achieve the desired goals.

Here, the role of institutions should focus on the effective use of knowledge management by employing it towards achieving goals, whether strategic or operational goals, enhancing the various capabilities and skills of their staff and achieving development, improvement and sustainability of these capabilities and skills. Knowledge management should focus on the impact of quality, directing its operations and implementing its strategy in an integrated manner.

This study came to address this topic because of its importance of the role played within these institutions, and to maintain the accuracy of information for decision-making in those institutions.

Problem of the Study

The quality of administrative decisions in institutions depends on knowledge management, so this study came to identify the reality of applying knowledge management processes on the quality of decisions in institutions? How interactive are their activities?

Institutions in their various activities seek success and progress, especially with the presence of competitors, institutions, whether governmental or private are racing to improve their administrative decisions, because these decisions reflect success and growth, and continuity in providing activity, and achieving goals whether material or moral. So this study came to try to show whether there is a relationship between the acquisition and possession of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions taken in order to conduct their business. This study attempts to answer the following question: Does diagnosis, planning, application, possession and sharing of knowledge have a relationship with the quality of administrative decisions?

Importance of the study

This study derives its importance from the importance of the work of institutions in achieving their goals, which requires institutions to pay attention, development, change and renewal, because the scarcity of research that deals with the impact of knowledge and its relationship to the quality of decisions on institutions in Jordan and the Arab world, the importance of this relationship to reach the stage of excellence and creativity in achieving their goals, the importance of the study highlights that successful departments always seek to identify the quality of decisions and methods necessary for their use and application, which leads to the required level of efficiency and effectiveness in these institutions.

Objectives of the study:

- 1) Studying the reality of knowledge management and identifying the level of effectiveness of activities and their impact on the quality of decisions.
- 2) Knowing and analyzing the relationship between senior management and the human element at the level of institutions in decision-making.
- 3) Highlight the role of knowledge management in the quality of decisions.

Study Design: This study relied on the descriptive analytical approach, the field study method, and through the preparation and development of its questionnaire as a main tool for data collection.

Data collection methods

- a) Secondary data collection: Secondary data was obtained through the researcher's review of the literature from books, periodicals and previous studies related to the subject of the study.
- b) Means of primary data collection: This study used the questionnaire as a means of collecting primary data.

Tests for the measuring instrument

- A. Validity, is defined as the process of ensuring that the instrument (scale) used actually measures the phenomenon it was designed to measure. The authenticity of the content of the measurement tool (questionnaire) used in this study was ascertained, as it was presented after the development of its initial form to three arbitrators from the faculty members at Jerash and Yarmouk University, to ensure that it covered the basic aspects of the topic, its clarity, and the integrity of its formulation and contents. The tool was then modified based on their observations in deleting some phrases, modifying and adding new phrases, and reformulating some paragraphs, to become clearer and more understandable among the members of the study sample, to be more honest in measuring the subject of this study.
- B. Reliability, the stability of the instrument used in the study was confirmed by extracting the Cronbach Alpha coefficient for internal consistency, Cronbach Alpha for multi-point scale. In order to ensure that the measurement tool does not obtain false data, if the same study is repeated and using the same tool in the same conditions in which it was used for the first time, and the value of this coefficient reached (0.85) for the all dimensions.

Related Studies:

- 1) **Shanti and Saada (2020).** The Role of Knowledge Management Processes in Improving the Quality of Decision-Making in the Directorate General of the Palestinian Military Medical Services. The study aimed to identify the role of knowledge management processes in improving the quality of decision-making, and to achieve the objectives of the study, a questionnaire was developed as the main tool for collecting the necessary data, and the descriptive analytical approach was used, and the study population consisted of all employees of the General Directorate in the military medical services, which numbered (820). The study found that the level of practice of knowledge management generalities in general was moderate, and knowledge management processes affect the quality of decision-making. Among the most important recommendations: Attention to increasing the practice of knowledge management processes as a strategic approach to improve the quality of decision-making, especially the process of distributing and applying knowledge.
- 2) **Abubaker, et, al. (2019).** Knowledge management, decision making style and organizational performance this study highlights the need and develops a framework for knowledge management and decision-making style by reviewing existing management literature. This research proposes a framework that supports the relationship between knowledge management enabling factors (i.e., organizational member's collaboration, T-shaped skills, learning and IT-support) and organizational performance, and the mediating effect of knowledge creation process. The article also propose that decision-making style (i.e., intuitive and/or rational) will moderate the relationship between knowledge creation process and organizational performance. A set of propositions that represent an empirically-driven research agenda, and also describe the

relationships between the focal variables are presented to enhance audience's understanding within a business context.

- 3) **Alrosan (2017)**. The role of knowledge management in developing management skills among faculty members and administration in College of Education for Girls in Jubail. The study aimed to investigate the role of knowledge management in developing management skills among faculty members and administration in College of Education for Girls in Jubail.. There were (109) members and administrative staff using a questionnaire consisting of 56 items distributed on two axes, which are the following: the first axis presents the role of knowledge management in developing management skills and this one includes three elements (technical skills, human skills, and intellectual skills). The second axis depicts the difficulties of knowledge management in developing management skills. The study results indicated that the role of knowledge management in developing management skills among faculty members and administration in College of Education for Girls in Jubail was really great. Results also showed that - there are no clear statistical differences in terms of qualification and job.
- 4) **Nouri (2013)**. The role of knowledge management in decision-making: A case study of a sample of managers of business organizations in Duhok Governorate. The study aimed to identify the role and importance of knowledge management in the process of strategic and vital decision-making at the level of business organizations, and to identify the advantages and difficulties of applying knowledge, the study found that the actual use or optimal investment of administrative knowledge in the economic sector is still limited due to the presence of obstacles and determinants related to the extension of opinions, leaders and human, technical, information and material capabilities available.

Based on the experience of the researcher and by reviewing previous studies related to the subject of the study, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

The first hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the diagnosis of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

The Second hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between knowledge planning and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

The third hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between knowledge sharing and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

The Fourth hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the acquisition of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

The fifth Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the storage and retrieval of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

The sixth Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the organization and follow-up of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

Population of the study and sample:

In this study, the descriptive approach was used to study the relationship between knowledge management and the quality of administrative decisions in government institutions in Jordan due to their appropriateness in this study.

The study population consists of all government institutions in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and the number of these institutions is 135 government institutions divided into 13 sectors.

A sample was selected for this study that included eight sectors: the childhood sector, the women sector, the people with special needs sector, the democracy and human rights sector, the health sector, the housing and infrastructure sector, the charitable societies sector, the culture and art sector, (200) questionnaires were distributed, from which (182) questionnaires were recovered, and considered to be valid for testing.

Theoretical framework

Introduction: Knowledge is an invisible asset of the organization, and includes extensive experience and distinct style of management and accumulated culture of the organization and shape one of the basic elements within an integrated chain, that begins with references and falls to data, then to information, then to knowledge, then to wisdom, which is an effective basis for innovation, it is clear that sufficient effective and accurate knowledge is at the core of wisdom, creativity and innovation.

Knowledge is a cumulative and integrative process formed over relatively long periods of time to become available for application and use to address specific problems and conditions, and therefore knowledge is used to interpret available information about a particular situation and decide how to manage and address it.

Knowledge includes human factors, non-human and non-living factors such as facts, beliefs, visions, perspectives, concepts, judgments, expectations, approaches, skills, ingenuity and knowledge a set of facts, facts, beliefs, concepts, visions, judgments, expectations, methodologies and ingenuities (Malkawi, 2006).

In light of the previous concepts, it can be said that knowledge is a set of experiences, skills, facts, beliefs, values, concepts, data and information that have been organized and processed, whether this knowledge is apparent or latent, and it can be used to solve problems facing the organization through the formulation, implementation and control of plans.

Knowledge is used to receive information, where this information is distinguished, identified, interpreted and evaluated, as well as carrying out the processes of installation, estimation, anticipation, and decision-making, adaptation to the surrounding environment, drawing plans, implementing and controlling them in a way that leads to acting correctly. (Najm, 2004)

In order to achieve a clearer and deeper picture of the concept of knowledge, it is necessary to distinguish between knowledge and other concepts and terms related to the term knowledge, including information and understanding, and when talking about knowledge, the talk diverges and deals with several areas and what matters to the modern organization in a fundamental and fundamental way is knowledge of work and knowledge of business and this knowledge expresses the ability of individuals and institutions to understand and act effectively in the work environment and this knowledge is usually managed by managers and individuals with distinct abilities and knowledge makers and co-workers and these They are responsible for achieving the survival of the organization in a competitive work environment and each of them works to build the best possible knowledge in every aspect of the organization.

Types of knowledge

According to (Al-Ali, 2006, Joseph, 2004), the ancient Greeks divided knowledge into:

- 1) Cognitive knowledge: This knowledge relates to the general principles and laws of theory, foundations and basic rules of science, laws and scientific rules.
- 2) Technical knowledge: This knowledge is related to skill and technical prowess, the ability to accomplish work and things, possession of exercises and adequate training to accomplish tasks and achieve similarity and conformity in the scientific practices of workers who perform the same tasks.
- 3) Hybrid knowledge: It expresses a combination of conflicts, attitudes and special abilities that are required in a field and lead to success and excellence in that field.

According to (Malkawi, 2006). There are two main types of knowledge:

- 1) Virtual knowledge: This knowledge is meant to be shared with others and this knowledge relates to the data and virtual information that can be obtained and stored in the files and records of the organization, as well as existing and stored in the files and records of the organization, which relate to the organization's policies, procedures, programs, budget, documents, foundations and standards of evaluation, operation, communication, various functional processes and others.
- 2) Tacit knowledge: It is related to what lies in the same individual of technical knowledge, cognitive knowledge and behavioral knowledge, which is not easy to share with others or transfer to them easily. Hence, it can be said that there are distinguished individuals who possess tacit knowledge in their minds, and the organization can increase its effectiveness and enhance its competitive advantage if it can include any of these individuals in their staff when the tacit knowledge of these individuals is related to the nature of the organization's work.

Knowledge is classified into local knowledge, where this knowledge is adopted under specific conditions and depends on physical and geographical conditions, and this knowledge is detailed knowledge, and global knowledge where this knowledge is being adopted on a wide global scale, especially in the fields of business, this knowledge is not limited to specific processes or specific industry, but rather penetrates geographical boundaries and is general knowledge.

Knowledge management and its role in the quality of decisions includes a set of activities that focus on gaining organizational knowledge through its own experience and the experiences of others, and includes the wise application of knowledge in order to achieve the mission of the organization, these activities are implemented through the integration of technology, organizational structure and organizational strategies supported by current knowledge and the production of new knowledge, the critical element in knowledge management that achieving support for knowledge systems with regard to organization, the human element, computing and others in order to acquire, store and use knowledge in Learning processes, problem solving, decision-making, etc.,. Where knowledge relates to pivotal and critical issues related to organizational adaptation, survival, and the capabilities and capabilities of the organization in the face of irregularly increasing environmental changes. (Aldori, 2004).

Knowledge management is a general framework that forms an umbrella for the organization, where knowledge affects administrative decisions in the institution in any organization seeking success, and the quality of administrative decisions affects the knowledge economy, which is a clear plan for activities, practices, policies and programs within the organization that are related to knowledge, and knowledge management should be concerned with a set of processes that work on the germination,

preservation, adoption and sharing of knowledge with others in order to support and enhance organizational performance and create value.

Whereas the impact of knowledge management on the quality of decisions is related to administrative processes of planning, organizing and coordinating knowledge and assets associated with intellectual capital, processes, capabilities and personal and organizational capabilities, so that the greatest possible positive impact on the results of competitive advantage is achieved, where knowledge must lead to the provision of the necessary facilities to achieve the contents of this management, where it cannot be said that there is one comprehensive, broad and agreed definition of knowledge management, as there are many differences about defining one concept for this The new term .

Since this concept is still in the stage of development and self-discovery, knowledge management goes beyond being just information or data, and there are two tracks of activities and efforts that are concerned with the concept of knowledge management, and these two tracks are: (Sabbagh, 2000)

The first track: It is an information path, and in this track, it is seen that knowledge management is the same as information management, and the owners of this path look at knowledge as information that is processed by information systems.

The second track: Under this path, knowledge expresses processes that reflect dynamic and complex skill sets of sorts.

The processes of knowledge management work sequential and integrate with each other, as each process depends on the other and integrates with it and supports it, and it has been mentioned in the theoretical literature a set of processes for knowledge management, and these processes:

- 1) Diagnosing knowledge proces: Diagnosis is one of the important things in the knowledge management program and in the light of the diagnosis is the development of policies and programs of other operations that the diagnostic process is inevitable because the goal of it is to discover the knowledge of the organization and identify the people who hold it and their locations, as well as determine the place of this knowledge in the rules and the diagnostic process is one of the most important challenges facing business institutions and that the success of the knowledge management project depends on the accuracy of the diagnosis and uses in the diagnostic process the mechanisms of discovery and the mechanisms of research and access and is a process Knowledge diagnosis is key to any knowledge management program and a key core process that contributes directly to the launch and definition of the form and depth of other processes (Cortada, 2003).
- 2) Knowledge planning process: It is related to drawing various plans related to knowledge development, supporting the objectives of knowledge management, individual and organizational activities, seeking to provide the capabilities and capabilities necessary for the efficient and effective conduct of business, providing specialized expert crews, and identifying the necessary technological facilities.
- 3) Knowledge sharing process: The American Society for Information Science has broadly defined knowledge dissemination as encompassing the processes necessary to communicate information to its users. (hurris, 1996).
- 4) Acquiring knowledge process: The generation of knowledge is related to the processes that focus on capturing, buying, discovering, absorbing and acquiring knowledge, where knowledge can be generated through a number of processes that extend between the challenge of creativity and serious research, as only individuals are born knowledge and the organization cannot generate knowledge without individuals, and the process of generating organizational knowledge focuses

on expanding the knowledge that is generated by individuals and then crystallized at the group level through dialogue, conversation and sharing. In experience or community of practice. And to achieve the effectiveness of generating and acquiring knowledge. (kao, 2005)

- 5) Storing knowledge process: The process of storing knowledge indicates the importance of organizational memory, as institutions face a great danger as a result of losing a lot of knowledge carried by individuals who leave them for one reason or another, and storing and retaining knowledge has become very important, especially for institutions that suffer from high rates of turnover and that depend on employment and use in the form of temporary and consulting contracts to generate knowledge in them because these people take their implicit knowledge that is not documented with them when they leave the organization.
- 6) Organizing and following up knowledge process: It is the processes that aim to classify knowledge, index or tabulate knowledge and draw knowledge. Institutions receive daily very large amounts of data and information come in a variety of forms and must be captured and supported by well-established procedures of investigation, editing and issuance, and the selected data and information must be organized into arranged groups called knowledge maps, which help in classifying data and information.

Obstacles facing knowledge management (Malkawi, 2006): multiple institutions have conducted studies on the obstacles to knowledge management, these studies found that there are a set of main obstacles that hinder the implementation of knowledge management effectively:

- The dominance of culture that inhibits knowledge sharing.
- Lack of support from senior leadership for knowledge management.
- Insufficient awareness of the concept of knowledge management and its content.
- Insufficient awareness of the role and benefits of knowledge management.
- Lack of integration between the organization's activities related to knowledge management and the promotion of organizational learning.
- Lack of training related to knowledge management.
- Lack of time to learn how to use and implement a knowledge management system
- Lack of understanding of the knowledge management initiative properly due to inefficient and inefficient communication.

The concept of administrative decisions (Al-Kubaisi, 2005):

The concept of administrative decisions expresses the employment of the skilled in a way that leads to the achievement of the goal for which it is employed, it is the ability to achieve the satisfaction of stakeholders, which is the ability to achieve maximum results and services using the available resources the best possible use, and is based on how the goals are achieved and meet the needs, and based on the depth of the effects caused by their achievement, and the speed of the results.

In summary, management decisions are about the organization's ability to achieve its goals.

Indicators of administrative decisions

It expresses the degree of achievement of the planned goals and is difficult to understand and assimilate away from the goals that represent the desired situation, and that the administration seeks to achieve in the future.

These indicators may be:

- 1) Output indicators where the focus is on the characteristics of the final output.
- 2) Process indicators, which focus on the quality and quantity of activities that lead to the achievement of outputs.
- 3) Structural indicators where the ability of the strategic business unit to achieve effective performance is assessed.

Analysis and discussion the hypothesis of the study.

First hypothesis: There was no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the diagnosis of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

To examine this hypothesis, the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient was extracted for the relationship between the diagnosis of knowledge, and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

It is clear from Table (1) that the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient amounted to 0.279, which is statistically significant for the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), so it can be said that the null hypothesis has not been achieved, and the alternative hypothesis has been achieved, the existence of a significant relationship (substantial) between the reality of knowledge diagnosis and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

Table 1: Results of the examination of the first hypothesis

The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions	Knowledge Diagnostic Process		
(**)0.279	1	Pearson's correlation coefficient	Knowledge Diagnostic Process
0	0.000	Level of significance.	The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions
182	182	Number	
1	(**)0.279	Pearson's correlation coefficient	
0	0.000	Level of significance.	
182	182	Number	

Statistically at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Second hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between knowledge planning and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

This hypothesis was examined by calculating the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient for the relationship between knowledge planning, and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions. Table (2) shows that the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient amounted to 0.340, which is statistically significant at the level of the function ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and thus it can be said that the null hypothesis has not been achieved, and the alternative hypothesis has been achieved, and this result confirms the existence of a significant relationship (substantial) between knowledge planning and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

Table 2: Results of the examination of the Second hypothesis

The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions	Knowledge Planning Process		
(**)0.340	1	Pearson's correlation coefficient	Knowledge Planning Process
0	0.000	Level of significance.	The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions
182	182	Number	
1	(**)0.340	Pearson's correlation coefficient	
0	0.000	Level of significance.	
182	182	Number	

Statistically at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

The third hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between knowledge sharing and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

This hypothesis was examined by calculating the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient for the relationship between knowledge sharing, and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions. Table (3) shows that the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient amounted to 0.282, which is statistically significant at the level of the function ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and thus it can be said that the null hypothesis has not been achieved, and the alternative hypothesis has been achieved, and this result confirms the existence of a significant relationship (substantial) between knowledge sharing and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

Table 3: Results of the examination of the Third hypothesis

The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions	knowledge sharing process		
(**)0.282	1	Pearson's correlation coefficient	knowledge sharing process
0	0.000	Level of significance.	The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions
182	182	Number	
1	(**)0.282	Pearson's correlation coefficient	
0	0.000	Level of significance.	
182	182	Number	

Statistically at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Fourth hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the acquisition of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

This hypothesis was examined by calculating the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient for the relationship between knowledge acquisition, and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions. Table (4) shows that the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient amounted to 0.279, which is statistically significant at the level of the function ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and thus it can be said that the null hypothesis has not been achieved, and the alternative hypothesis has been achieved, and this result confirms the existence of a significant relationship (substantial) between the acquisition of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

Table 4: Results of the examination of the Fourth hypothesis

The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions	acquiring knowledge process		
(**)0.279	1	Pearson's correlation coefficient	acquiring knowledge process
0 182	0.000 182	Level of significance. Number	The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions
1	(**)0.279	Pearson's correlation coefficient	
0 182	0.000 182	Level of significance. Number	

Statistically at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Fifth Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the storage and retrieval of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions. This hypothesis was examined by calculating the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient for the relationship between the storage and retrieval of knowledge, and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions. Table (5) shows that the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient amounted to 0.360, which is statistically significant at the level of the function ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and thus it can be said that the null hypothesis has not been achieved, and the alternative hypothesis has been achieved, and this result confirms the existence of a significant relationship (substantial) between the storage and retrieval of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

Table 5: Results of the examination of the Fifth hypothesis

The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions	The process of storing and retrieving knowledge		
(**)0.360	1	Pearson's correlation coefficient	The process of storing and retrieving knowledge
0 182	0.000 182	Level of significance. Number	The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions
1	(**)0.360	Pearson's correlation coefficient	
0 182	0.000 182	Level of significance. Number	

Statistically at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Sixth Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the organization and follow-up of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

This hypothesis was examined by calculating the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient for the relationship between the organization and follow-up of knowledge, and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions. Table (6) shows that the value of Pearson's correlation coefficient amounted to 0.369, which is statistically significant at the level of the function ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and thus it can be said that the null hypothesis has not been achieved, and the alternative hypothesis has been achieved, and this result confirms the existence of a significant relationship (substantial) between the organization and follow-up of knowledge and the quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions.

Table 6: Results of the examination of the Sixth hypothesis

The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions	The process of organizing and following up knowledge		
(**)0.369	1	Pearson's correlation coefficient	The process of organizing and following up knowledge
0 182	0.000 182	Level of significance. Number	The quality of administrative decisions in Jordanian government institutions
1	(**)0.369	Pearson's correlation coefficient	
0 182	0.000 182	Level of significance. Number	

Statistically at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

In summary, it is noted through the results of the study that there is a significant relationship between the level of application of knowledge through its various processes (knowledge diagnosis, knowledge planning, knowledge sharing, knowledge acquisition, storage and retrieval, organization and follow-up of knowledge) and the quality of administrative decisions in government institutions in Jordan. This result is consistent with Al-Shanti (2020) and its results are that there is a positive relationship between knowledge management and the effectiveness and quality of administrative decisions.

It also agrees with Nouri's study (2013), which concluded that there is a relationship between the joint use of knowledge management and information technology and the high value of organizations' business, in addition to an increase in the high value of business institutions as a result of the use of information technology and knowledge management.

The results of the study proved and confirmed the existence of a significant relationship between the applications of knowledge management and the effectiveness of decision-making in government institutions in Jordan, and here it must be emphasized that the institutions that practice knowledge management and use it in their organizational life are more effective and more able to achieve their goals and make sound decisions, institutions that are able to diagnose knowledge through their possession of tools that enable them to discover knowledge and are able to identify individuals who possess knowledge - inside and outside the institution - and that care By attracting experts in the field of knowledge management associated with its activities, it is necessarily more capable of achieving its goals, and institutions are more competitive, more sustainable and more effective when they set goals that help spread knowledge in the institution and determine the appropriate means to achieve the goals that should be known, and seek to obtain knowledge from multiple sources, and rely on

customers and workers as sources of knowledge and reward employees for their innovative ideas and their efforts to gain knowledge, encourage employees to exchange knowledge within the institution and work to develop Current knowledge.

The success of institutions in achieving their goals requires hard work to update knowledge through the revision of knowledge in all methods, and requires them to review knowledge periodically and work on the development of new innovative ideas.

Human energy is one of the main factors in the success of the organization and investment in that energy leads to the success of institutions in their ability to achieve their goals and this investment is done through: Transferring knowledge related to the activities of the institution from multiple sources to its various units and presenting innovative ideas obtained from outside the institution to its employees, and working to train workers in order to develop their abilities and skills and help them acquire knowledge through internal sources and from external sources, and institutions seek to succeed through Exerting all its efforts to develop means of communication between the different units.

There is no doubt that institutions that seek to disseminate, distribute and exchange knowledge between different units and all employees will be able to achieve their goals. In order for institutions to succeed in achieving their goals, they must organize, classify and preserve knowledge so that it is easy to use and also require them to follow up on its application and control.

FINDINGS

Based on the analysis of the study hypothesis, the results can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The results of the study showed that government institutions in Jordan use knowledge management processes (knowledge diagnosis, knowledge planning, knowledge sharing, knowledge acquisition, storage and retrieval of knowledge, organization and follow-up of knowledge) and although government institutions use all knowledge management processes. There is a discrepancy between different sectors in the extent of their use of them.
- 2) It is noted that the institutions of the culture and art sector are the most used sectors for the process of diagnosing knowledge, followed by the charities sector is the least used sectors to diagnose knowledge.
- 3) With regard to the effectiveness of the activities of government institutions, the results of the study showed that government institutions succeeded during the last five years in achieving their goals through their various activities, taking into account that there is a disparity between the different sectors in the extent to which they achieve those goals.
- 4) The results showed a significant relationship between the applications of knowledge management and the quality of administrative decisions in government institutions in Jordan, as institutions that practice knowledge management and use it in their organizational life are more effective and able to achieve their goals than other institutions that do not practice knowledge management.
- 5) There is a clear variation between different sectors of organizations in the extent to which they use knowledge management.
- 6) Government institutions have proven their effectiveness and success during the last five years, represented through their activities that contributed to achieving their goals.

- 7) There is a direct relationship between the extent of knowledge management practice and its effectiveness, as institutions that practice knowledge management processes are more effective than those that do not practice knowledge management processes are more effective than others that do not use them.
- 8) Government institutions carry out the processes of networking and coordination among themselves, which gives them strength and provides them with the capabilities to achieve their goals.

Recommendations:

- 1) The senior management of government institutions should adopt strategic thinking for knowledge management and work to encourage and apply it through various programs.
- 2) Encourage employees to acquire knowledge from internal and external sources.
- 3) Seeking to develop electronic means of communication and the development of Internet programs as a means of acquiring and exchanging knowledge.
- 4) Government institutions should exchange knowledge among themselves through meetings, conferences and exchange of experiences.

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